

STUDY REPORT ON SURVEY

Police Atrocities in LEGAL TERRORISM

SURVEY on Victims of LEGAL TERRORISM

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Introduction: MyNation analysis of the survey shows that how men are harassed/abused and tortured by the Protectors of law, the Police along with the wives and girlfriends by various Women centric laws. In India it is often assumed that women are victim and men as perpetrator/abuser, but the evidence collected by MyNation demonstrates that this is a false predomination, promoted by feminists and women organizations. There are dozens of one sided laws only for Women and None for Men

Methodology: Information for this report was sourced from the testimonies, Survey statistics of victims of Legal Terrorism. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are neglected by the Government of India, World Organizations. Even none of the survey data study Institutes or Media is ready to publish misuse of law/Abuse or Legal terrorism on Men, in the name of Empower women all these atrocities are state sponsored.

Key Findings: Majority men were ashamed to come forward to report such abuse, misuse of law to terrorize them, as there are no laws or authorities like Police/Judge/Minister to report, reporting their abuse will be an Invitation to bigger trouble and charged with false cases like Section 498A of Indian Penal Code / Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 these are few out of many Weapons of men's destructions (WMD) of India, that make men to suffer in silence. The exact number of such cases are difficult to assess as majority of the cases go unreported, but it's even tougher to figure out just how many men are suffering abuse and face LEGAL TERRORISM. A big part of the reason is traditional gender roles in society and the stigma of the perceived weakness of any man who admits to falling victim to a woman. MyNation survey is first such survey where men came forward and submitted their say, as there is a limit to suffering or torture. When it is unbearable they have no choice than admit it and open up themselves.

This survey and study report is based on Valid Statistics from the survey hosted on <https://mynation.net> for the period of 6 months and participated by more than 2000 people aged between 26 to 74 years. These statistics and testimonials are from the victims, and not collected as done by Women organizations which collect from Fake statistics or cooked up sob stories and have no valid backing. Our each entry of statement is from a unique IP, i.e., no multiple IPs data recorded or counted in the survey.

WHAT IS LEGAL TERRORISM?

A Harassment by the state with the help of Law, judicial court or Police by Vexatious litigation, or by the individuals or unscrupulous persons to wreak personal vendetta or unleash harassment by filing of lawsuits to extort money/Assets or force to admit for their demands.

Supreme Court of India, in Sushil Kumar Sharma vs Union Of India And Ors on 19 July, 2005, Terming the misuse of provisions of dowry harassment by women as "legal terrorism"; a court has slammed such women who, in a bid to settle scores, drag all family members into a dowry harassment case though they may be "totally unconnected" with the case. "The provisions of Section 498A are not a law to take revenge, seek recovery of dowry or to force a divorce but a penal provision to punish the wrongdoers. The victims (women) are often misguided into exaggerating the facts by adding those persons as accused who are unconnected with the harassment under a mistaken belief that by doing so they are making a strong case," additional sessions judge Kamini Lau said.

The court also expressed its displeasure over the misuse of the dowry harassment laws. "I am compelled to observe that provision in the recent years has become consummate embodiment of gross human rights violation, extortion and corruption and even the Apex Court of our country had acknowledged this abuse and termed it as legal terrorism".

If a woman files a false complaint of dowry harassment, domestic violence, any other matrimonial complaint or women centric laws like Section 354 IPC, Section 375/376 and Section 377 IPC to a nearby police station against a Man and his relatives, they are arrested even if the investigation is incomplete sill they can be jailed on non-bailable terms.

SURVEY URL: <https://mynation.net/legal-terrorism/>

Understanding the state of violence committed on men through Data.

The survey was open to all and also sent via twitter to feminists also tagging to NCW/WCD and media channels to show this survey is not closed Survey only for men but it looks as if females were not interested to fill in their favour, because they know they cannot prove it if asked to show the evidence.

LAST PUBLIC ANNOUNCEMENT BEFORE CLOSING THE SURVEY

MyNation Foundation
@MyNation_net

VICTIM OF LEGAL TERRORISM ? mynation.net/legal-terroris...
PLEASE TAKE PART, IT TAKE HARDLY 1 MINUTE
mynation.net/covidv/ @rsprasad @smritiirani @SmritiIraniOffc
@sharmarekha @SwatiJaiHind @LambaAlka @NCWIndia
@MinistryWCD @UN_Women @unwomenindia @kapoors_s
@SayftyCom @Judith_Char

srBachan and 9 others

8:08 AM · Sep 7, 2020 · Twitter Web App

Also on the face of it, it looks as if only males have replied hence it is in favour of men, just think opposite of that if it was replied by all females we would have thought that males are really bad and violent, our mind is so biased to trust females and not males though they were given an opportunity but selected to remain silent. This is the feminist mindset which gave birth to this law.

Let us delve today on a matter less discussed, less in the closed rooms, even lesser in parties, lesser in the society and seldom in the media, generally it is a unspoken taboo to speak in favor of Men and the issues that affect them physically, mentally and otherwise, such is the state of dismay that even men are unable to discuss it. To the rightfully thinking people it seems sometimes that men are some other species, but certainly not homo sapiens, they don't feel pain, emotions, are incapable of love, mental health issues don't affect them, they don't even get cancer it seems.

All of it seems true in the world we live in today, if we truly try to examine in an unbiased and scientific manner. Time and again science and technology has shown us that data and stats can be helpful to analyze a problem, if a problem really do exists in our body, physical, societal, national or if you may the world as a whole.

We at MyNation foundation have tried to do the same through one of our surveys and would like to share with you our findings,

ANALYSIS OF THE SURVEY:

1). GENDER OF VICTIMS:

For this we sampled more than 2000 candidates, who are either directly or indirectly affected by violence or abuse whether legal or illegal, mainly in the home environment, or by a spouse or are related to spousal or familial violence and we found out 97.55% are Men and only 2.45% are Women.

2). EDUCATION:

Most of the victims of this kind of violence which is meted out in legal or domestic form are men, out of all the surveyed at least 80 percent are either graduates or post graduates, a majority of which are salaried professionals, and in a whopping 97.06 percent of the cases the oppressor is a women

The general perception is that men or women who are uneducated or who are generally alcoholics or are from the low rung of the society indulge in such things like oppressing theirs partners, using unjust laws which were made for the protection of real victims of most heinous crimes against their partners just to extract money, resources or just to teach them a lesson and to the surprise most of them are women, and that to highly educated, above 86 percent of whom are either graduates or post graduates.

As we analyze the education part cases filed by educated and post graduate women is 92%. Now leaving apart that uneducated people don't see twitter fine. But do we expect this from educated people. The educated men are more vulnerable to domestic violence cases because the women are aware of the law and they know the pain their own men will have because of filing a case. To conclude educated women often file domestic violence cases to corner or harass the man's families. Uneducated families or couple on the other hand ignorant of law fight in the house and solve it next day. For a minute if we think that domestic violence law itself is scrapped, couples would solve problems internally in a day because they have no option but to live together. Hence the law is doing more harm than protecting families for which it was formed and promulgated.

3). PROFESSION:

Most of these women despite being salaried professionals themselves (over 60 percent) or employed in some form or other, and most of them wedded partners (over 90 percent wives) who took an oath taking their respective God or Gods as witness to be together and strengthen each other, for the rest of their lives, file such false and unscrupulous cases and allegation not only on their life partners but also on the close family members and don't even spare far away relatives, many of whom are women, in such draconian sections of laws such as dowry, domestic violence, criminal force, intimation and even rape.

4). MARITAL STATUS

MARITAL STATUS

It is natural that married only will file a case and a very important point here is all cases are filed only by women. It is clear legal terrorism, The law wants to protect woman but it break families, it grants maintenance to give freedom to live alone and bear the expenses and so break the marriage and live freely on somebody's money and give them pain. Do we marry for purpose of living separately or together? In fact love marriages should never be allowed to go to court for any case because they married according to their own will, which itself is an affidavit that a woman will live with an unknown person lifetime in as is where is condition. And the same with man, law should be gender neutral

5). OPPRESSOR GENDER:

OPPRESSOR GENDER

Out of 2000 peopled we surveyed 97.55% are men who faced Violence from Women. Above graph shows that's 97.06%. Again the law gives a free hand for legal terrorism. But oppressor is not only of gender. We at MyNation have

members just to give a broader view. The gender i.e., the female who is a wife is used by her side of members i.e., parents, brothers etc. to create a fight or spoil a family. We always say that terrorist has no religion so crime also has no gender. Is it written anywhere that only males are terrorists, goondas, hooligans or female hitters? No, if we had Kaikaey who as a mother had ordered her son to go to vanvas for 14 years, we had kunti who abandoned her son in the river, we had Soornpankha and Pootna rakshas also. It is how the perception in the male side is the root cause for case, one of the latest cases was of Indrani Mukherjee who killed her daughter and hid the fact and filed a complaint that she is missing. What was that, does crime have a gender? i.e., men. This reminds me of a movie where people are born with a mark as criminals.

6). OPPRESSOR EDUCATION:

OPPRESSOR EDUCATION

Most of the oppressors are well educated, who have knowledge of law and are aware that they can use these Women centric laws to harass, as there is no punishment for misusing these laws. That's why it's called LEGAL TERRORISM.

7). OPPRESSOR PROFESSION:

OPPRESSOR PROFESSION

Most of the oppressor are not only well educated but employed too, most of them are in a very good position as in education and also in employment they have reservation even though they are not capable to handle the work. But when matter of Maintenance comes they beg for alimony from husband, even if she is educated and earning well and her appeal is granted because of the biased legal system

8). WHO IS THE OPPRESSOR:

WHO IS THE OPPRESSOR

And all the credit goes to WIFE as an oppressor. No wonder most of the surveyed choose Wife as oppressor, because that is truth, Indian society is blind. They always portray men as villain, Majority men are suffering silently without revealing their suffering in the hands of their wives and die young. But Women always tell everyone/ neighbours and her family that she was harassed even she is the one who harasses her husband and his family and everyone believe in her. Now we have given chance to men to express their views and here is the truth.

9). WHICH CASE FILED ON VICTIM:

WHICH CASE FILED ON YOU (M)

SECTION 498A IPC - 23.12%

DP3/4 - 12.67%

DOMESTIC VIOLENCE - 18.85%

IPC Section 323 - Punishment for voluntarily causing hurt. - 6.33%

IPC SECTION 354 - Assault or criminal force to woman with intent to outrage her modesty - 2.06%

IPC SECTION 375/376 - Rape - 0.44%

IPC SECTION 377 - Unnatural offences - 2.21%

IPC SECTION 406 - Punishment for criminal breach of trust. - 9.28%

IPC SECTION 420 - Cheating and dishonestly inducing delivery of property - 1.77%

IPC SECTION 506 - Punishment for criminal intimidation - 8.69%

IPC SECTION 499/500 - Punishment for defamation - 0.88%

OTHER - 13.70%

When a marriage breaks down the woman is often able to get her husband and many of his family members arrested by simply claiming Dowry demand, Domestic violence or cruelty even if she has no proof of her claim and persuading the local police to arrest the so-called wrongdoers. This is much more effective than initiating an ordinary case for divorce. Notorious Section 498a IPC take number one position followed by domestic violence.

10). HOW LONG CASE IS RUNNING:

HOW LONG CASE IS RUNNING (M)

0 - 1 YEAR - 16.50%

LAST 2 YEARS - 32.04%

3 - 5 YEARS - 37.86%

MORE THAN 5 YEARS - 11.65%

MORE THAN 10 YEARS - 1.94%

Due to biased law it takes 5 years in our system for a husband and his family to prove himself innocent. This could cut down to months, if the complaint is found to be false the guilty should then be charged with same section and double penalty. That is gender neutral law. Which in turn would reduce pressing of false cases and

our country would rank higher in world for sustainability of matrimonial life with proper legal consultation. This is the foundation stone for betterment of coming generations.

11). CASE FILED ON WHOM:

CHARGES AGAINST WHOM (M)

For women best way to harass her husband to get divorce or maintenance is filing case against his aged Parents along with him. Even though they never stayed with them or are staying far away, Police will add their name by default. It all depends with that Police have been bribed with and how influential the women’s family is. Police even include brothers/sisters even breast fed 2/3 months old child of husband sisters have been included in many reports.

12). PRE-INVESTIGATION PROCEDURES FOLLOWED?

PRE-INVESTIGATION ENQUIRY PROCEDURE FOLLOWED (M)

Most of the time Police just copy and paste what women or her Lawyer has given as complaint, they do not conduct a proper investigation or enquiry, No DIR

(Domestic incident report), and they do not issue a 41A notice which is mandatory in every investigation.

13). TYPE OF COMPLAINT:

TYPE OF COMPLAINT (M)

POLICE FIR - 52.73%

CAW CELL - 23.05%

NCW - 3.91%

TO THE COURT U/S.156 CrPC - 20.31%

In India, it is very easy for a Women to file a complaint with Police, anyone can go to Police station shed some crocodile tears, cry loudly and police are bound to register her complaint without verifying any of her claim or evidence. Height of all some claimed to be raped by a person who was miles away in another city or even if she claims she was raped in her dream, Police will register her complaint and start arresting whoever she names.

14). TYPE OF INVESTION / ENQUIRED BY POLICE

TYPE OF INVESTIGATION / ENQUIRY BY POLICE (M)

FORCED SIGN ON BLANK PAPER - 2.30%

STATEMENT RECORDED UNDER PRESSURE - 3.72%

FORCED TO SIGN PRE_FILLED QUESTIONNAIRE - 2.30%

ENQUIRY IN THE PRESENCE OF ACCUSER / LAWYER - 4.78%

FORCE TO AGREE TO ACCUSER CONDITIONS - 5.66%

POLICE DEMANDED MONEY / BRIBE - 11.15%

NOT ALLOWED TO TALK - 10.80%

POLICE ADDED EXTRA CASES WHEN DID NOT AGREE TO THEIR DEMAND - 4.07%

THREATS OF ARREST OR INCLUDE OTHER FAMILY MEMBERS - 10.97%

COERCION TO SETTLE MATTER AMICABLY IN RETURN OF MONEY - 6.37%

THREAT FOR IMPOUNDING PASSPORT - 3.19%

CHARGE SHEET WITHOUT ANY ENQUIRY - 15.22%

ARRESTED WITHOUT ANY ENQUIRY - 3.89%

CHARGES FRAMED WITHOUT ANY EVIDENCE OR ENQUIRY - 15.58%

The type of Investigation police conduct when a women complain, most of the time they just copy and paste all her statement as it is without any evidence or enquiry, they will file charge sheet. In some cases they file charge sheet on same day of FIR and that's not speedy work of Police, but these charge sheets are filed without any ground, investigation or enquiry. Even without serving 41A notice or informing accused Police can announce them as absconding or not co-operating with investigation, all this depends on how much bribe is offered.

15). ACCUSED IF NRI

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PASSPORT IMPOUNDED - 9.43%

THREAT TO IMPOUND PASSPORT - 28.30%

THREAT TO ISSUE LOC - 20.75%

PRESSURE TO COME TO INDIA FOR ENQUIRY - 24.53%

THREAT TO ARREST OLD PARENTS IF NOT COMING TO INDIA - 16.98%

In the case of non-resident Indians (NRI) the process has often proved calamitous for the husband. When wife has differences and have an argument. She deserts and will fly back to India, often with children and as much of the valuable /assets as she can gather. She immediately starts a Section 498A case in India and then sues for divorce and custody in India and many manage to get Look out circular (LOC) issued. The husband cannot step foot in India because he will be arrested. Meanwhile his relatives in India are clamoring for him to settle up with his wife because they have been in jail or are fearful that that will happen. The Supreme Court of India has described such conduct as “legal terrorism. All because of Police involvement, they file case without any evidence, just on the words of the women. Without a need to say they take money, they threaten to impound passport or issue LOC, arrest relatives. Here as a result mostly police Impound the passport, even though only Passport Authority has the right to Impound.

16). INVESTIGATION METHOD

INVESTIGATION METHOD (M)

As soon as women files a complaint or women goes to the Police station with her problem, some Police only direct her to a lawyer whom they have nexus. Lawyer along with the Police draft a complaint and ask the women to sign, then Police will call her husband and most of the times his aged Parents and threaten to arrest, as per survey reply most of the time Police will abuse and manhandle also. If husband is not ready to agree to their terms they will add additional sections to make their case stronger and abuse and trap the man.

17). POLICE HELPED TO UNITE OR SOLVE THE PROBLEM

POLICE HELPED TO UNITE OR SOLVE THE PROBLEM (M)

Out of 2000 survey result only 9% said they are helped by Police to solve their domestic matter. When women goes to Police station, she is just another client from whom they can make some money threatening her husband so both can bribe them. Police hardly help unless man pays more than women does or has some influential connections.

18). EXPERIENCE IN CAW / MEDIATION CENTER

EXPERIENCE IN MEDIATION CENTER / CAW (M)

When Man/Husband is called to CAW or mediation center they will not allow anyone from husbands side, but they will allow women along with her relatives and lawyers, most of the CAW cells do namesake enquiries, they are always on women's side, and force man to agree to their terms / Pay her. Kick out his parents from him, abuse and threat is common in CAW only 0.56% said CAW is friendly environment.

19). ABOUT INVESTIGATING AUTHORITY

ABOUT INVESTIGATING AUTHORITY (M)

In India no Judiciary or Police support man when women complaint against man. There is standing order from top, no matter who is guilty, women should not suffer, this women is only Daughter-in-law, even National commission of women says husband Mother / Sisters are not coming under their mandate. Police always support young Women, there is no respect for elderly if they are Man's parents. Indian Police is not only corrupt and abusive they think women is always right and Man is a born criminal.

20). RESULT OF FIR / COMPLAINT

RESULT OF FIR / COMPLAINT (M)

As said earlier most of the Women centric complaints end up in a charge-sheet without any CrPC 41A notice / investigation or enquiry. Police just copy paste women statement and turn it as a charge-sheet, they add other family members to pressurize and make the case complicated.

Cases under Section 498A was found to have the lowest conviction rate — merely 12.1 per cent — among all cases of crimes against women.

According to the latest data on crimes, released by the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), more than 3.3 lakh cases of crimes against women were registered in 2016. Of these, 1.1 lakh cases related to ‘Cruelty by husband or his relatives’.

Cases under Section 498A was found to have the lowest conviction rate — merely 12.1 per cent — among all cases of crimes against women.

“Assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty”, kidnapping, and rape, which formed the next three major chunks of crimes against women, had conviction rates of 21.8%, 21.4% and 25.5% in 2016, according to NCRB.

Close to 10,000 cases were also registered under the Dowry Prohibition Act in 2016, but conviction rate here too was just over 15%.

(News source: <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/section-498a-dowry-most-firs-least-convictions-4969913/>)

NCRB data shows 85% Dowry Prohibition Act cases are fake, which shows the real truth behind all these women centric cases.

False case of matrimonial issue which not only is enough to tarnish the image of a familial man, or person, or a family in the eyes of the society but often drive people to other extreme measure as harming themselves, creating depression and even driving many to end their precious God given life, and all this is not because women are victims, it's just because they just could, and in turn they harm the same gender these laws were put in place to help; the real victim of such heinous crimes.

It not only seems women have a free run with laws, the judiciary, the police but the society at large, some of these cases takes most of the good years of a man's life, the average being 5 years, consider being in litigation for 5 whole years of life and that is less the actual time for a person to come out of a divorce maybe 10 or 15 years.

If the accused is an NRI, then these harassments may take another forms like passport impoundment, pressure to come back for enquiries or just plain harassment of relatives.

Many enquire, don't the police try to mediate? Although by now we should know the answer but sometimes they do (we are not saying that the entire police force is bad or corrupt) but why would a monkey stop two cats from fighting over a piece of bread.

Either we have lost all our wisdom where family was a unit of love, sacrifice, duty and service to each other or somewhere, someplace in imitating the west, western law. The blinded wave of feminism which sees the opposite sex as the enemy rather seeing the greatness of the creator, Mother Nature or whatever we may term it. Where social justice warriors don't know anything about justice we have tipped the balance of well rooted culture, where humility, love and the wellbeing of children was the quintessential and unalienable motives for coming and being together through the ups and downs of life. This is just for the sake of fake narrative which in the end turns up to nothing to us as a person no matter the gender.

With this we would like to point out that although it is a general perception that females are usually at the receiving end of a hard bargain called marriage the current scenario is not such, men are equally even more oppressed and if we really want to create a just and equal society we must examine and clear the rot which is slowly but surely spreading through our society, we have done it many times when the world sees towards our great nation in awe that how a peninsula so ancient and seemingly archaic can shine such light on this planet and holding a beacon of rays of hopes in our hands and feel proud about it.

It is understandable that the judiciary wants to examine every case and follow the procedures of laws but the harassment begins even before the man reaches to the courts, the state of affairs of police functioning is not hidden from the citizenry of our nation, but our survey points out that in such cases no or little procedure is followed by the police as far as 32 percent cases don't even make an effort to make a call to ascertain the allegations even from the alleged male perpetrators.

Moreover there are specialized police station or cells and commission who go over and above board and law and start punishing and harassing the man openly and brazenly even before the cases reaches the court, most of the times the accused are made to sign forced pre filled questionnaires, even blank papers, or forced and coerced to agree to unjust terms of the women, and if someone doesn't agree to their terms they are threatened, charges are framed without any real enquires, bribes are demanded and the routine or extra law sections are inserted to harass and make the case stronger.

Police should always be the first line of defense to stop crime as well as violate law or misuse of law, but in India, Indian Police are first to misuse law and violate it. Above survey is enough to show how they support law misusers just for few hundred rupees, they have no value for the person who is aged, paralysed or breast fed baby (<https://supari.org/zoya/> - **2 Month old Charged under 498a – Get Bail**), they blindly take any complaint if its filed by a Women. This shows the Police support for LEGAL TERRORISM, as they are the main part of this misuse.

Reference:

**LEGAL TERRORISM IN MATRIMONIAL DISPUTES - SOLUTION FOR
LEGAL TERRORISM (<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3695617>)**

**VIOLENCE AGAINST MEN - FALSE ACCUSATION OF SEXUAL
HARASSMENT (<https://mynation.net/voice/ssrn-3673754>)**

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Disclaimer: This Research study does not use any Fake statistics to justify any views expressed by the authors, Most Statistics used can be found on NCRB or respective Government Ministry websites and above survey is hosted on <https://mynation.net>, A NGO fight for Equal rights for Men and Justice for the Family.